

Fiber Surface Energy Effects on the Mechanical Properties of Unidirectional Fiber Composites

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the thermodynamic adhesion between fibers and matrix on the mechanical properties of a continuous fiber reinforced composite is studied for two systems: carbon fiber reinforced poly(ether-ether-ketone) and glass fiber reinforced poly(ether-imide). The fibers are modified chemically and characterized by measuring the contact angle formed by molten resin on the fibers. Various fiber treatments yield a wide range of contact angles, which are determined optically. Unidirectional fiber reinforced laminates are manufactured and transverse flexural strength is measured with the values reported as a function of the specific work of adhesion. It is shown that adhesion at the fiber-resin interface correlates with both the composite strength and the void morphology within the laminate after consolidation.

INTRODUCTION

Among the factors generally recognized to influence mechanical properties of high-performance continuous fiber composites is the adhesion of the matrix material to the fiber surface. A convenient expression for this is the thermodynamic work of adhesion, W_a , defined as the work required to disjoin a unit area of interface in vacuo and expressed by the Dupré equation [1],

$$W_a = \gamma_s + \gamma_l - \gamma_{sl}, \quad (1)$$

which together with the Young equation [2] can be written as

$$W_a = \gamma_l(1 + \cos \theta), \quad (2)$$

where γ is the surface energy per unit area, the subscripts s and l refer to solid and liquid, respectively, and θ is the contact angle between liquid and solid.

The thermodynamic work of adhesion often correlates well with the results of various mechanical tests on adhesive joints or composite systems made from the same or similar materials [3]. Such mechanical tests include single fiber pull-out, fragmentation, peel, and micro-tension tests, as reviewed elsewhere [4-6]. These tests allow mechanical characterization of the interface. Thermodynamic characterization of fiber-resin composite interfaces in terms of work of adhesion can be determined either by measuring γ_s , γ_l and γ_{sl} using Eqn. (1), or by measuring γ_l and θ together with Eqn. (2). The former can be determined by the Wilhelmy method using a series of probe liquids of known surface energy and surface energy components

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together with a mixing rule allowing the calculation of γ_{st} . The determination of W_a thus depend on the mixing rule used to determine γ_{st} . This method is difficult for several reasons: high microbalance sensitivity and painstaking effort are required, even when working with standard probe fluids at room temperature, because the diameter of the fibers typically used in composites are so small [7]. Inverse gas chromatography [7, 9-13] can also be used to determine the acid-base components of the surface energy, but this process inevitably requires theory to relate the interfacial energy to the resin and fiber surface energies. Optical determination of the contact angle is difficult because the solid is in the form of a fine fiber, and any profile view of the meniscus reflects the influence of the fiber curvature [8].

Hodge et al. [14] and Nardin et al. [9-12] both studied carbon fiber (CF) reinforced poly (ether-ether-ketone) (PEEK) systems using indirect methods. Hodge et al. [14] performed capillary measurements on PEEK and three different carbon fiber surfaces using standard probe fluids. They reported a correlation between mechanical strength and the predicted work of adhesion but their data were bunched, making it difficult to draw conclusions. Nardin et al. [9-12] separately characterized PEEK and different treated carbon fiber surfaces with inverse gas chromatography (IGC), and then predicted the level of interaction between the different fiber-resin combinations. Their values for the total work of adhesion were surprisingly high, ranging from 115 to 208 mJ.m⁻². While, they observed monotonic relationships between the predicted work of adhesion and both yield strength and elongation at yield, interlaminar shear strength did not correlate with the predicted work of adhesion.

Bucher and Hinkley [15] and Mayer et al. [16] have reported direct measurements of fiber-resin interfacial properties and attempted to relate these to the mechanical properties of continuous fiber composites. Bucher and Hinkley studied the carbon fiber reinforced poly (ether-ketone-ketone) (PEKK) system, measuring contact angles of liquid resin on three commercial carbon fibers and comparing these results with mechanical properties of unidirectional composites. The work of adhesion, however, varied by only 3 percent, as calculated using Eqn. (2). Also, they allowed a variation in interfacial area by using different fiber diameters, ranging from 5.2 to 7.9 μm . This corresponds to a variation of 50 % in interfacial area at constant fiber volume fraction, a change expected to have profound effects on mechanical properties [17]. Finally, in their contact angle measurements, insufficient time was allowed for their liquid resin drops to reach equilibrium; prompting them to report their values as "apparent contact angles". They observed scattered results for interlaminar fracture toughness and a monotonically increasing relationship between apparent contact angle and transverse flexural yield strength.

Investigations to date into the relationship between the mechanical properties of fiber-matrix composites and the work of adhesion for the fiber-matrix interface have suffered a number of shortcomings as noted above and have not always produced convincing correlations. It is therefore the objective of the present work to seek results more nearly free of these difficulties. The work of adhesion is determined directly from Eqn. (2) using measurements of the equilibrium contact angle between molten resin drops and the surfaces of chemically treated carbon and glass fibers, ample equilibration time being given. Chemical treatments of the fiber surfaces are used to provide a large range of contact angles and thus significantly alter the work of adhesion at the fiber-resin interface. Finally, the composite systems to be compared will differ only in their interfacial properties. The present work focuses on the fiber-resin systems of CF-PEEK and glass fiber reinforced poly (ether-imide) (PEI). The experimental methods used also permit characterization of the void topology in the composites, providing an opportunity for interesting subsidiary observations on the effect of contact angle on inclusion formation. The complexities involved in measuring contact angles on cylindrical fibers are discussed.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 FIBERS AND FIBER SURFACE MODIFICATION

The fiber-resin systems selected for this work were in commercial "FIT" form, i.e. bundled fibers surrounded by a resin sheath with fine resin powder dispersed throughout the bundle. Two fiber-resin systems were studied: carbon fibers (CF) (T300, Soficar) with PEEK (grade 150, ICI Corp) and glass fibers (GF) (E-type, Owens-Corning) with Poly(ether-imide) (PEI) (Ultem 1000, General Electric). The use of commercially available FIT yarns, where the matrix

powder and the reinforcement fibers are already in intimate contact, did not allow fiber surface modifications such as plasma treatment [18] or fiber surface oxidation [19]. It was thus decided to alter the surface of the fibers by chemically removing the sizing deposited on the fiber surface during manufacture. The compositions of these sizings are proprietary. On the basis of discussions with chemists from Soficar and Owens-Corning, the treatments summarized in Table 1 were applied to the fibers.

Chemical treatments were performed by first dipping the FIT fiber bundles into the chemical solution vertically with the tips protruding from the solution and allowing 15 min for the treatment solution to wick up the fibers. They were then totally immersed and agitated for the remainder of the time indicated in Table 1. After treatment, the fiber bundles were placed in a vacuum oven at 80°C for 24 h to evaporate remaining solvent and moisture. Obviously, no improvement of the adhesion is expected from these chemical treatments; on the contrary, the aim here is not to improve but only to alter the surface energetics, and show its influence upon mechanical properties.

Table 1: Chemical treatments of FIT systems

System	Treatment conditions
CF-PEEK	
C1	unmodified
C2	6 h in methyl ethyl ketone (MEK) at 25°C
C3	6 h in MEK at 50°C, then 2 h in CH ₃ OH at 25°C
C4	6 h in MEK then 12 h in CH ₂ Cl ₂ at 50°C, 2 h in CH ₃ OH at 25°C
GF-PEI	
G1	unmodified
G2	6 h in 0.25M HCl at 25°C, 2 h in distilled water
G3	6 h in 0.25M HCl at 50°C, 2 h in distilled water

2.2 CONTACT ANGLE MEASUREMENT

The direct determination of the work of adhesion for a fiber-resin system requires measurement of the contact angle of molten resin against the fiber and use of Eqn. (2). Unfortunately, the measurement of contact angles of liquid drops on cylindrical surfaces is complicated by competing curvatures, a phenomenon studied by various authors [8, 20, 21]. A liquid drop resting on a fiber can adopt either the stable geometry of an axi-symmetric unduloid (cf. Fig. 1a) or the metastable geometry of the "clam-shell" (cf. Fig. 1b) [22]. The unduloid form prevails when the drop is large relative to the fiber and the contact angle is relatively low. For both geometries, the tangent optical method is inappropriate, and it is more accurate to find an analytical expression dependent on the equilibrium geometry of the drop.

A numerical solution for the unduloid geometry was proposed simultaneously by Carroll [20] and Yamaki and Katayama [21], and later by Wagner [8]. We use the solution proposed by Wagner [8] which, for a given dimensionless height, $h = H/R$, and dimensionless diameter, $l = L/R$, gives a value of the contact angle, θ , where H is the distance between the top of the drop to the center of the fiber, L is the drop/fiber interface length, and R is the fiber radius.

Walliser [22] proposed a semi-empirical method for contact angle measurement of clam-shell drops, the apparent contact angle of which is a function of drop volume. He suggested that the curve $h-l$ can be well-fit by the relation

$$h = a \cdot l^2 + b \cdot l, \quad (3)$$

where a and b are statistical regression results. He then proposed that the contact angle is well approximated by:

$$\theta = 2 \arctan(2b). \quad (4)$$

Geometric data for drops of various sizes can thus be collected and used to estimate the contact angle for the liquid against a cylindrical surface. This approach is only a suggestion and should be validated, but it seems the most appropriate available measuring technique for the clam-shell drop geometry.

A few yarns of each of the systems listed in Table 1 were cut open and placed into an oven at the processing temperature (390°C for CF-PEEK and 340°C for GF-PEI) for sintering. The drops were allowed four hours to attain an equilibrium contact angle between the molten resin and the fiber surface, but the drop shape was found not to vary with time after two hours. The fibers were then rapidly removed from the oven and quenched at room temperature to "freeze" the molten resin in place. Viscoelastic effects were considered negligible and the captured drop geometry represents the thermodynamic state at the processing temperature. Images of the resin on the treated surfaces were obtained using scanning electron microscopy (SEM).

Values of h and l were measured on a minimum of fifteen drops for each system. In the case of unduloid drops, contact angle values were determined using Fig. 3 in Wagner [8]. In the case of clam-shell drops, an h - l plot was constructed. Care was taken to select a wide range of drop volumes, and a best fit of Eqn. (3) was determined using the Marquart-Levenberg algorithm, as suggested by Walliser. The contact angle was then calculated with Eqn. (4). The results were in agreement with angles measured using the tangent optical method for low drop volumes.

Figure 1: Micrographs of PEEK resin drops in contact with treated carbon fibers: (a) C1, $\theta = 1^\circ$, unduloid; and (b) C4, $\theta = 80^\circ$, clam-shell.

2.3 LAMINATE MANUFACTURE AND TESTING

FIT yarn was wound around an 80 mm-radius cylinder and melted together in spots with a soldering iron. Squares of 50x50 mm were cut and stacked to form a "towpreg". All the laminates were manufactured identically. The mold, a square match die mold of 50x50 mm, was heated to the processing temperature (390°C for CF-PEEK, and 340°C for GF-PEI) and the towpreg was placed into the mold and left for 15 min to reach iso-thermal conditions. A pressure of 5 MPa was then applied and the consolidation curve was recorded. After 7 min, the mold was cooled at approximately 60°C·min⁻¹ under constant pressure. After 5 min of cooling, the mold was opened and the laminate extracted. The weight, thickness, void content (ASTM D792) and fiber content (matrix burn out, only for GF-PEI) were measured. All the laminates showed less than 3 % porosity. The measured fiber weight fraction of GF-PEI was 65±1 %. The CF-PEEK FIT manufacturer indicates 67 % fiber weight fraction.

Evaluation of composite mechanical strength required selection of an appropriate test. Transverse flexural strength (ASTM-790M) was chosen as a mechanical test representative of the adhesion properties of the composite. It is defined in [15] as a "means of characterizing the tensile strength of the fiber-matrix interfacial bond". The 50x50 mm laminates described were cut into three 10x50 mm bands, with the fibers transverse to the length. These were randomly tested with a Zwick mechanical tester using a beam span of 37 mm and a crosshead speed of 0.8 mm·min⁻¹. The stress-strain curves were recorded. The fracture surface of destroyed CF-PEEK samples from the mechanical tests were studied with SEM. Polished cross-sections were prepared and used to analyze the void topology with SEM.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The only systems forming axi-symmetric unduloid drops were C1 and C2. The systems C3, C4, and all of the GF-PEI systems formed clam-shell drops. Figure 1 shows micrographs of PEEK resin drops in contact with carbon fibers for two of the four treatments used on those fibers (C1 and C4). Determination of a standard deviation was only possible with the unduloid drops, because one drop picture corresponds to one contact angle measurement. The specific work of adhesion, $W_a/\gamma = 1 + \cos \theta$, was calculated from contact angle data. This quantity is, of course, directly proportional to the work of adhesion when the wetting fluid is not changed, as is the case here. Table 2 summarizes the results of contact angle measurements and calculated values of the specific work of adhesion. For clam-shell drops, all of the drop measurements are collected on one graph to obtain a single value of the contact angle. The results listed in Table 2 show that the chemical treatments altered the surface energy of the fibers, apparently removing the sizing from the surface. This increased the value of the contact angle formed by the molten resin and hence decreased the value of the specific work of adhesion.

Table 2: Contact angle measurement results

System	θ [deg]	W_a/γ	Drop shape
C1	1 ± 2.0	2.00	unduloid
C2	10 ± 5.1	1.99	unduloid
C3	54	1.59	clam-shell
C4	80	1.17	clam-shell
G1	66	1.41	clam-shell
G2	71	1.33	clam-shell
G3	127	0.40	clam-shell

Figure 2 compares examples of the resulting stress-strain curves of the four CF-PEEK systems, reflecting the obvious differences in yield stress and strain observed experimentally. Values of the yield stress and strain and the bending modulus, σ_y , ϵ_y and E_b , respectively, for the different systems and treatments studied are summarized in Table 3. Two GF-PEI towpregs, G3#1 and G3#2, were treated and manufactured identically, yet yielded completely different results. No explanation was found for this difference in behavior, and it was thought best to present the mechanical values separately for the two laminates rather than combine them.

Figure 2: Typical stress-strain curves for the carbon fiber-PEEK laminates.

SEM observation of the CF-PEEK fracture surfaces showed that in the untreated laminates, C1, the fracture propagated mainly through the resin, exposing little bare fiber surface. This suggests that the failure was cohesive. The resin is severely torn and strained, likely resulting in higher fracture energies. The area density of bare fibers increases with the severity of the chemical treatments, following the sequence C2, C3, and C4. By contrast to the untreated laminates, the C4 laminates exhibit surfaces in which the print of the fiber creulation is still clearly visible, indicating a weak interface. The GF-PEI laminates all showed a high density of bare fibers and are quite similar to each other.

Table 3: Transverse flexural strength values

System	σ_y [MPa]	ϵ_y [%]	E_b [GPa]
C1	41.3 ± 6.8	1.04 ± 0.16	4.4 ± 0.4
C2	36.1 ± 3.9	0.98 ± 0.13	4.3 ± 0.5
C3	29.9 ± 3.9	0.76 ± 0.15	4.2 ± 0.5
C4	27.8 ± 1.5	0.74 ± 0.08	4.4 ± 0.4
G1	26.6 ± 3.4	0.49 ± 0.04	6.3 ± 0.8
G2	23.4 ± 2.5	0.54 ± 0.07	6.2 ± 0.4
G3#1	16.8 ± 1.8	0.39 ± 0.06	4.8 ± 0.7
G4#2	32.6 ± 0.8	0.66 ± 0.03	6.3 ± 0.1

Figures 3 and 4 demonstrate the apparent relationship between unidirectional composite mechanical properties and the specific work of adhesion. The relationship between mechanical interfacial strength and the thermodynamic work of adhesion is intuitive, because both characterize the energy required to destroy an interface and create new surfaces. The work of adhesion, however, corresponds to reversible thermodynamic conditions while measured mechanical properties include phenomena such as void volume in the composite, viscoelasticity, etc. The mechanical strength will obviously be decreased by void volume, particularly if the voids are at the interface and one would expect the void topology to be a function of the interfacial energy. Wu [23] has related the presence and size of inclusions to the contact angle via another thermodynamic parameter, the specific spreading coefficient, λ , which is defined here as the negative free energy change associated with the spreading of a specific liquid over a solid surface and calculated as

$$\frac{\lambda}{\gamma_l} = \cos \theta - 1. \quad (5)$$

Eqn. (5) is written in a form which requires a finite equilibrium contact angle, as observed in all of the systems studied here. A finite quantity of air will always be trapped during composite manufacture and remain in the part after processing. Under favorable wetting conditions, e.g. small, finite contact angle and λ close to zero, the area of the solid/air interface will be minimized and entrapped air will tend to locate away from the fibers. Under poor wetting conditions, i.e. higher negative λ , the large contact angle provides no mechanism to expel the air from the surface and the void space will be concentrated at the fiber-resin interface. This is illustrated well in Fig. 5 with SEM micrographs of polished PEEK-carbon fiber composite surfaces. The porosity of the composites was about 3 % and did not vary significantly.

Figure 3: CF-PEEK system: (a) yield stress vs. specific work of adhesion; and (b) yield strain vs. specific work of adhesion.

Figure 4: GF-PEI system: (a) yield stress vs. specific work of adhesion; and (b) yield strain vs. specific work of adhesion.

Figure 5: Laminate void topology: (a) C1, $\theta = 1^\circ$, $\lambda / \gamma_l = 0$; and (b) C4, $\theta = 80^\circ$, $\lambda / \gamma_l \ll 0$

Our results can be compared with those of Nardin et al. [9-12], who studied the adhesion of carbon fiber-PEEK systems; using the same fiber type (T300 from Soficar) as the present study but with different surface treatments. As described, the values they reported for the predicted work of adhesion varied from 115 to 208 $\text{mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ for their different fiber surfaces. Their IGC measurements, made between 40 and 100°C, were used to arrive at these values. Introducing these values into Eqn. (2), and using $\gamma_l = 44.7 \text{ mJ}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ [24], yields zero contact angles for all their systems, i.e. the resin would spread spontaneously on all the fibers investigated. This contradicts our results; we found finite contact angles for all of our treatments. These unusually high values can be attributed to the IGC technique, which is an indirect method to reach W_a , based on a theory which is not fully characterized yet.

The glass fiber-PEI systems gave results less clear than those of the carbon fiber-PEEK systems. Although the chemical treatments listed in Table 1 can be considered as successful for the large range of contact angles obtained, they may have altered the matrix properties as well. Indeed, the transverse bending modulus, listed in Table 3, varies between $6.3 \pm 0.8 \text{ GPa}$ for the untreated glass fibers (G1), and $4.8 \pm 0.7 \text{ GPa}$ for the warm acid treatment (G3). The transverse bending modulus should be relatively independent of the interfacial properties, as shown for the carbon fiber-PEEK systems. Another curiosity is that two laminates, G3#1 and G3#2, were treated, manufactured, and tested identically, yet showed very different mechanical properties. No reason was found to explain this difference. Obviously, it would have been best to treat the fiber surfaces in the absence of the polymer; unfortunately, the FIT yarns with continuous fibers are commercially manufactured. Consequently, we chose the option of treating the fibers within the FIT yarns. If the fibers could be treated prior to combination with the polymer sheaths and powder, an easier and wider range of treatments would be available.

Finally, there are factors regarding composite manufacture that this study has not considered. Most importantly, previous investigators have discussed the formation of an "interphase" zone that forms at the fiber-resin interface, the properties of which are dependent on the cooling rate used in composite manufacture and, possibly, interfacial energy [20].

CONCLUSION

A wide range of equilibrium contact angles of molten resins against carbon and glass fibers was obtained by chemically attacking the fiber sizing, reflective of changes in the fiber surface and fiber-resin interfacial energies. Contact angle measurements were completed for the drop-cylinder geometry using techniques presented in the literature and the specific work of adhesion was calculated using Eqn. (2). Transverse flexural testing of the fibers was selected as representative of the interface properties, and a relationship between the mechanical properties of unidirectional fiber composites and the specific work of adhesion was established. The results were clear for the carbon fiber-PEEK system: laminate transverse flexural strength was sensitive to fiber surface modification. Micrographs of the fracture surfaces and void topology for the various cases confirmed this relationship; cases of lower specific work of adhesion and higher negative spreading coefficient showed a higher density of bare fibers and untorn resin and the voids are seen to be primarily at the fiber-resin interface. The results obtained with the glass fiber-PEI system are not so conclusive, perhaps due to a matrix alteration during the chemical treatments. The glass fiber-PEI fracture surfaces were all quite similar, perhaps because the spreading coefficient is very negative for all the treatments, yielding a high flaw density at the interface in all cases.

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